

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INVESTIGATING CRYPTO-ECONOMICS IN THE PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

In the field of crypto-economics the project has provided everyone with opportunities for the release of their "own" cryptocurrency, more precisely, a new crypto-token on based on the blockchain platform of smart contracts of the same name without low-level programming skills. An unregulated and rather simple way to attract alternative investments has become popular among technology startups, who have connected their activities with blockchain technology. This method was called the initial coin offering (Initial Coin Offering, ICO).

Keywords: cryptocurrency, ICO, BTC , electronic payments.

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In the study, the authors used machine learning to classify ICO projects and evaluate them in terms of financial ROI (return on investment) based on the processing and analysis of digital data that is public and available on the Internet. The study aims is to develop a robust and efficient model that can predict the return (or trend of return) ROI of an individual ICO startup. As a result of the work, a predictive model was built, and service (applications) was developed for analyzing data for selection ICO startups.

Crypto-economics should always be taken into account when building decentralized networks, as it is a kind of mechanism that provides the ability to agree on incentives among participants, without the need to trust third parties.

Crypto-economics is not a subspecies of traditional economics, it is a mixture of game theory, mechanism design, mathematics, and other methodologies in this field. The main goal of this direction is to provide an understanding of how to finance, design, develop and facilitate the functioning of decentralized networks [1].

In this article, we will explore the origins of crypto-economics and its role in the creation of Bitcoin and other decentralized networks [2].

METHODOLOGY RESEARCH

First of all, to solve the problems of the study, it was necessary to determine what data must be collected and can be collected based on their availability. The following are the different kinds of data that the authors were able to formalize on the basis of semi-automated work. With various web resources:

- general information (project name, country, token, team members, documents, category project, and t. d.);
- information about the ICO procedure (sales opening and closing date, issue volume (issues) of tokens, targets for the sale of tokens, including pre-sale (or pre-ICO), price tokens etc.);
- information from social networks (statistics from Twitter, backlinks (backlinks) to the website and

ratings (score), mentions in social networks, etc.);

- information about IT development ("road map" project, activity development on the github.com choice blockchain platforms, details smart contract and t. d.);

- the results of the ICO procedure (the number of funds raised during the sale, the price of tokens on the crypto exchange, ROI, volume bidding, and t. d.).

Currently, all the necessary data for the study cannot be found. money on one resource (web page). There is no single register that would contain all ICO projects, including for the traditional market there is no such website. This is partly a consequence of the decentralized nature of the ICO, including because of this, it is sometimes impossible to determine the place of origin circulation of the project (place of its registration). Therefore, the authors, to fulfill the tasks of the research Researchers have decided that it is best to find as many different data points as possible to fully see the picture in general on market and right come up with evaluation investment and risks ⁷.

At the same time, there were many so-called ICO trackers on the Internet. Usually, ICO tracker It has listed some quantity ICO projects, selected on not- publicly disclosed by the providers of this service; this list of projects can be formed from tokens with "paid placement" (listing for project advertisements) or be a project filter with a certain number of parameters. These trackers provided information only about ICO projects; every treker had its own functional set of services. Not a single tracker was found that second satisfied would all needs on quantity placed projects, on their functional opportunities for solutions tasks given research.

PREPARATION DATA

Cleaning and preliminary treatment data — the most important step for this project and generally for machine learning in general. Mistakes made at this stage affect the all further calculations and may not only reduce efficiency models, but and make them untenable. Consideration should also be given to both the technical and business logic" of the solution. The first point concerns statistical information about such characteristics.

To prepare kit data, it took exclude observations (fragments set) that did not include a similar amount of information in composition and structure (for combined

into a common data set), like most others, and these missing data are data (observations) could not be calculated. Therefore, the data set applied the following filters:

- procedure ICO must be completed;
- there is authentic information about price tokens in time holding ICO in currencies USD and BTC

there is reliable information about the price of the token on the first trading day (on the exchange) in currencies USD and BTC.

Stages training data schematically shown in the Fig.1.

Figure 1. Stages training data

The index is calculated on the basis of data from other fields set, such how: as the price of the token on the date of the start of the ICO procedure and the price of the token on the first trading day when placed on a crypto exchange (i.e., upon the initial appearance of the token on the exchange) on formula (one).

$$ROI = \frac{Total\ Revenue - Total\ Cost}{Total\ Cost} \tag{1}$$

The purpose of this study is to forecast profit or risk investments made at the ICO stage. It is assumed that the investor (hedge fund) can buy project tokens only at the official price during the ICO, this was one of the limitations of the study, and sell them only on a cryptocurrency exchange, receiving at this profit or lesion. AT given case general revenue (potential income) — is the price of the token on one of the crypto exchanges on the day of their first listing (the average

price may be used in case, if accommodation token happened on several exchanges.

Since the data was obtained from various sources and converted from non-strict formats, there were outliers in the analysis dataset that could be conversion errors, source data errors, or atypical (unusual) projects. Even tuning models for sustainability to emissions could negatively reflect on the quality models, used in her scales.

AT calculations research index ROI maybe accept negative values, where -1 (total loss). Most of the values in this data set were between -1 and 1. According to the histogram (Fig. 2), the distribution is positively distorted. AT connections With topics that huge positive values given indicator could would have too much effect on the weights of the neural network, observations with a value ROI greater than 10 (1000%) were removed from the data set for further analysis.

Distribution ROI

Figure 2. Distribution ROI.

IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

To solve the problem, an artificial neural network was developed using libraries. Layers are given neural networks shown in the fig. 3.

Figure 3. Layers neural networks.

The created model will predict a binary classification, therefore, to use, a binary cross entropy loss function was chosen. To solve this problem, Adam's optimizer (optimization algorithm) works well (*Adam optimizer*, or *adaptive moment estimation*). Function activation PReLU (*Parametric Rectified Linear Unit activation function*) showed better results compared to others modifications on the ReLU. AT given models binary accuracy is basic- Noah metric. Because the need was found, to meaning exit (output) came across in range $[0, 1]$, for the weekend layer used sigmoid function activations (*sigmoid activation function*).

Before starting work With the model was viewed as current kit data. First class ($ROI < 0$) assigned 296 observations, second ($ROI \geq 0$) — 189 samples.

The classes were not balanced: in the current situation, it was about two unsuccessful ICO investments against one profitable. If an artificial neural net must be learn on such set data, then her accuracy not could reflect real model performance. The model could accurately predict that each test observation (project) belongs to the first class, and could give out accuracy much more, how fifty %, but only due to such imbalance.

First of all, the model should not be evaluated using only one metric accuracy. Accuracy is a simple and straightforward metric, but it makes no difference between classes and issues inherent in the data set itself. There are also more complex metrics, such as how:

- square under ROC curve AUC (square under crooked) is aggregated characteristic of the quality of classification, which does not depend on the ratio error rates. Higher AUC-ROC means the best classification model. This indicator is often used for the comparative analysis of several models. classification;

- metrics conversions (*precision*) shows how a lot of observations corresponding to whether the predictions (i.e., the constructed model) were assigned to a certain class, actually belong to this class. The result is located in the range $[0, 1]$;

- *recall* metric shows how many samples that belong to a particular class were predicted to belong to that class by the model. Result located in range;

- F1-score combines *harmonic mean* metrics conversions and completeness.

Then the unbalanced kit data must be balanced. There are various ways to do this. We use technology artificial modifications dataset for alignment ratios classes. They can divide the excessive sampling of classes minorities insufficient sampling of classes majority and combine these approaches.

RESULTS OF RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

The cross-validation metric confirmed the accuracy of the model. The calculated model showed 79% accuracy (this is the average value for all calculation results), which gave the best model).

To prove the results given calculation was completed with separate forecast and race- counted the following metrics:

- AUC made up 0.78 for the test set;
- Precision*: 0.82 for unprofitable observations (negative ROI); 0.76 - for past (positive ROI);
- Recall*: 0.64 — for unprofitable observations, 0.9 — for profitable;
- F1 score: 0.72 — for unprofitable observations, 0.82 — for profitable.

Given the results obtained and a balanced data set, one can conclude that the model predicts the target values much better than the random model tea selection (*random guess*). Based on a model with 79% accuracy, it became possible definition vector investments in ICO startups, their profitability or unprofitability.

Note that the original data set contained more than 3000 observations (ICO- projects) ¹³. After cleaning and removal of emissions, only 518 remained. Of these, 234 projects have a positive ROI, which means that these ICOs were profitable.

The results of the study can be used as a basis for forecasting vanity. Implemented applications, collectors data, script preliminary form- Data bots, prediction model. The implemented service used the database data

The functionality of the service can be extended by adding a client API for forecasting new flow data from users. Implementation of such processes, how collection data and education (retraining) models, maybe to be finalized and automated. An example of the described service architecture (applications) is given in the figure 4.

Figure 4. Architecture service (applications).

CONCLUSION

To implement the objectives of the study, various IT components were developed architecture services (applications) for monitoring, analyzing, and forecasting risks in ICO startups [3].

The first component —is the Appendix on collection data. The collection is sufficient and structured-data collection is a challenge in itself. It was solved by reviewing various sources of data, a choice the most useful, and unloading-loading these data in various ways, It was implemented in form applications, written in the Python.

The next component is data cleansing and preprocessing, where the Python script loads data from Mongo DB persistent storage (database) into bi- the Pandas Data Frame library. Then apply the launch of various filters to discard (delete) observations, which have not enough complete information or are not good-meet other minimum requirements for further analysis. Data sets data from different sources are combined into more general sets using common functions such as tokens or names. Finally, the functions are converted to the format in which the maybe to be applied for work with a neural network.

To solve the problem of classification and forecasting the profitability of investments (positive ROI) was developed artificial neural net. The average ROI medium di profitable ICO (according to the sample of

the study) amounted to 47%, which is a relatively high indicator for a given type of investment.

Considering then, what crypto market is highly volatile and probability Togo, what similar investments not will bring no arrived, much above, how probability investment- success, such model forecasting maybe turn out to be very valuable for goals critical selection (exceptions) row ICO projects from potential investment in them. The developed components that can be used as a basis for creating a service for monitoring ICO projects, are the architecture described in the previous section (rice. four). Herself model forecasting risks maybe to be improved in the first turn using the most complete (wider) set of data. At this the solution of individual tasks of collecting and processing data can be carried out manually, which will require additional resources.

References

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